

Parameter Adaptive Technology for Continuous-Energy Deterministic Neutron Transport Calculation

Haopo Liu, Yunzhao Li*, Xiaoyu Wen, Hongchun Wu, Liangzhi Cao

Xi'an Jiaotong University, 28 West Xianning Road, Xi'an, Shannxi 710049, China

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ABSTRACT

Traditional deterministic neutron transport calculations rely on the multi-group approximation, which suffers from issues such as the typical energy spectrum assumption in multi-group databases and complex approximations in resonance calculations. An entire-energy-domain coupled continuous-energy deterministic neutron transport method has been proposed based on function expansion, which eliminates the problems caused by the multi-group approximation. Focusing on this direction, this paper constructs a mechanism for adaptive discretization of energy segmentation and dynamic matching of function expansion orders based on the Bondarenko theory. It dynamically divides non-resonant energy ranges according to the relative root-mean-square error (RRMSE) and achieves hierarchical refined matching of optimal expansion orders in resonant energy ranges. It realizes adaptive discretization of energy segments and dynamic matching of expansion orders, thereby obtaining an accurate solution to the continuous-energy deterministic neutron transport equation under real material compositions. Taking UOX fuel as test case, comparisons with continuous-energy Monte Carlo results show that the maximum relative deviation of neutron flux density calculation does not exceed 2.7%, and the eigenvalue deviation is less than 50 pcm. Using the adaptive energy segment structure in neutron transport calculations reduces time consumption by ~two-thirds vs. the traditional fixed structure—boosting calculation efficiency and highlighting the adaptive method's superiority in practice—while balancing calculation accuracy and efficiency better.

Keywords: Neutron Transport; Continuous-Energy; Deterministic; Basis Function Expansion; Adaptive

1. INTRODUCTION

In nuclear reactor core physics analysis, calculation methods fall into two main systems—probabilistic and deterministic—with deterministic methods holding an important engineering role for their higher efficiency and having mature discrete solution frameworks in spatial and angular dimensions. However, deterministic methods still rely on multi-group approximation for energy phase space processing (involving pre-building multi-group databases via typical neutron spectra and complex resonance calculations), and the development of modular small reactors now demands more accurate in-reactor neutron energy spectrum characterization. To improve the calculation accuracy in the energy dimension, the research carried out can be mainly divided into three categories. Generalized energy condensation theory [1], [2]. Coupled processing framework of continuous-energy and multi-group [3], [4], [5], [6]. Ultra-fine group method with energy grid discretized into tens of thousands of groups [7]. In addition, there is the reduced-order model method [8].

Most of the above methods generally rely on multi-group theory, and the division method of the energy group structure is fixed, depending on engineering experience, resulting in poor versatility for different types of energy spectra. At present, some studies have discussed the adaptive division method of energy groups based on multi-group theory, with typical methods including contribution theory [9], particle swarm optimization [10], and discontinuous finite element method [11]. For the energy group

*Email address: yunzhao@mail.xjtu.edu.cn

structure optimized by such methods each time, it is necessary to use a multi-group database generation program to re-obtain the multi-group database required for neutron transport calculations.

For the material distribution in a specific region of the reactor core, this study employs function expansion technology to perform full-energy-domain numerical discretization of the neutron transport equation. Building on the previously developed continuous-energy deterministic neutron transport calculation method[12] under a fixed energy segment structure, this paper further explores the refined division strategy of energy segments and the adaptive determination mechanism of the basis function expansion order. It automatically generates an appropriate energy segment division scheme according to the material composition characteristics and simultaneously determines the optimal expansion order of the basis function for each energy segment.

2. THEORETICAL MODEL

Neutron-material interaction characteristics, concentrated in each material's energy-dependent reaction cross-section, vary greatly across media—total cross-sections are smooth in high- (fast neutron) and low-energy (thermal neutron) ranges but feature dense, sharp resonance structures in the intermediate range. Using a nuclear database, the minimum lower and maximum upper bounds of all nuclides' resonance ranges in a material region (derived from their total cross-section characteristics) can divide the entire energy domain into resonant and non-resonant intervals.

2.1. Continuous-Energy Deterministic Neutron Transport Calculation Method

Focusing on the energy independent variable, this study temporarily excludes spatial and angular dimensions—thus ignoring the spatial leakage term and excluding the spatial independent variable in the corresponding continuous-energy neutron transport equation. Given that full-range function expansion demands high-order basis functions (and the Runge phenomenon limits accuracy gains from higher orders), each energy range is further divided into segments; calculation accuracy is improved by increasing the number of refined segments and reducing the expansion order, resulting in the steady-state continuous-energy neutron transport equation for the i -th segment.

$$\sum_k N_k \sigma_{t,ki}(u) \Phi_i(u) = \sum_k N_k \sum_{i'=1}^I \int_{u_i'}^{u_{i'-1}} e^{u'} \Phi_{i'}(u') \sigma_{s,ki}(u') \int_{-1}^1 f_{s,ki}^{\text{LAB}}(u' \rightarrow u, \mu) d\mu du' + S_i(u) \quad (1)$$

where $u = \ln E$, E/MeV ; N_k is the density of the k -th nuclide in atom/cm^3 ; $\sigma_{t,ki}(u)$ is the microscopic total cross-section in cm^2 ; $\sigma_{s,ki}(u)$ is the microscopic scattering cross-section in cm^2 ; $\Phi_i(u)$ is the neutron flux in $\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$; $S_i(u)$ represents other neutron sources; $f_{s,ki}^{\text{LAB}}(u' \rightarrow u, \mu)$ is the scattering probability density function with scattering angle cosine μ in the laboratory coordinate system.

In the non-resonant energy range, a polynomial basis function with continuous and smooth variation is selected to expand the neutron flux density, as shown in the following equation:

$$\Phi_i(u) = \sum_{n=0}^{N^i} \Phi_{in} P_n(u) \quad (2)$$

where N^i is the maximum expansion order of the function; $P_n^i(u)$ is the n -th order expansion polynomial function, which can be constructed through a three-term recurrence relation.

In the resonant energy range, the Daubechies[13] wavelet scaling function is selected as the basis function system to expand the neutron flux, and the expansion form is as follows:

$$\Phi_i(u) = \sum_{n=0}^{N^i} \Phi_{in} \varphi_{j,n}^i(u) \quad (3)$$

where: $\varphi_{j,n}(u)$ is the basis function with a dilation order of j and a translation order of n .

Substitute Eqs. (2) and (3) into the neutron transport equation, then project both sides of the equation onto the coordinate axes of each orthogonal basis function in sequence, and perform numerical integration on both sides of the equation within the logarithmic energy interval $[u_i, u_{i-1}]$. The transport equation in the following form can be obtained:

$$\sum_k \sum_{n=0}^{N^i} \Phi_{in} N_k \sigma_{t,kin'} = \sum_k \sum_{i'=1}^I \sum_{n=0}^{N^{i'}} \Phi_{i'n} N_k \sigma_{s,ki'imm'} + S_{in'} \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\sigma_{t,kin'} = \int_{u_i}^{u_{i-1}} \sigma_{t,ki}(u) R_n^i(u) R_n^{i'}(u) du \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_{s,ki'imm'} = \int_{u_i}^{u_{i-1}} e^{-u'} R_n^{i'}(u') \sigma_{s,ki'}(u') \int_{u_i}^{u_{i-1}} \int_{-1}^1 f_{s,ki'}^{LAB}(u' \rightarrow u, \mu) d\mu R_n^i(u) du du' \quad (6)$$

$$S_{in'} = \int_{u_i}^{u_{i-1}} S_i(u) R_n^i(u) du \quad (7)$$

$$R_n^i(u) = \begin{cases} P_n^i(u) & ,if \ i \in non-resonant \ energy \ region \\ \varphi_{j,n}^i(u) & ,if \ i \in resonant \ energy \ region \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Source iteration method is used to solve Eq.(4), and then the unknown flux expansion coefficients $\{\Phi_{in} | i = 1, \dots, I; n = 0, \dots, N^i\}$ in each energy segment can be obtained. The refined function distribution of the neutron flux in different energy segments is obtained from the expansion equations.

2.2. Adaptive Energy Segment Discretization and Dynamic Expansion Order Matching

The accurate solution of the transport equation essentially depends on two key parameters—the refinement degree of energy segment division in each energy range and the basis function expansion order in the corresponding segment—but existing methods require manual pre-setting of these parameters (heavily relying on engineering experience and repeated trial calculations, leading to strong subjectivity and low efficiency); thus, to break this bottleneck and balance calculation accuracy and efficiency, it is urgent to construct an automated parameter matching mechanism that automatically searches for the global optimal solution, thereby significantly improving the reliability and versatility of continuous-energy neutron transport calculations.

According to the Bondarenko theory[14], it is assumed that the variation of flux mainly comes from the fluctuation of the total reaction cross-section. In a uniform medium within a material region, the approximate neutron balance relationship can be given by the following equation:

$$\sum_k N_k \sigma_{t,k}(u) \Phi(u) = S'(u) \quad (9)$$

The idea of this method is to approximate the source term on the left side of the equation as a smooth function $S'(u)$, which is approximately equivalent to the flux distribution and can be selected by the user according to the type of reactor. For thermal spectrum reactors, $S'(u)$ follows the Maxwell-1/E-fission spectrum distribution. Compared with the neutron transport equation, this equation greatly simplifies the calculation cost and can directly obtain the reference flux, as shown in the following

$$\Phi^{ref}(u) = \frac{S'(u)}{\sum_k N_k \sigma_{t,k}(u)} \quad (10)$$

The neutron flux density function in the above Eq.(10) is expanded as follows:

$$\Phi^{ref}(u) \approx \Phi^{cal}(u) = \sum_{n=0}^N \Phi_n^{cal} R_n(u), \quad \Phi_n^{cal} = \int_{\Delta u} \Phi^{ref}(u) R_n(u) du \quad (11)$$

To judge the fitting effect of the N -th order calculated flux $\Phi^{cal}(u)$ on the reference flux $\Phi^{ref}(u)$ in the above equation, the relative root-mean-square error (RRMSE) can be calculated.

$$RRMSE = \frac{\left\{ \frac{1}{X} \sum_{x=1}^X [\Phi^{cal}(u_x) - \Phi^{ref}(u_x)]^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\frac{1}{X} \sum_{x=1}^X \Phi^{ref}(u_x)} \quad (12)$$

where: x is the position of the discrete energy point; X is the total number of discrete energy points.

2.2.1. Non-Resonant Energy Range

In the non-resonant energy range analysis, since the flux varies continuously and gently with energy, a unified expansion order is used to build a model for the entire range; then the relative root-mean-square error (RRMSE) between the model's output flux and the reference flux is calculated to quantitatively evaluate the model's prediction accuracy, thereby determining whether the energy range needs refined division, with specific steps as follows:

Step 1, determine the unified expansion order $N^{\text{Non-res}}$ (the default value of $N^{\text{Non-res}}$ is 2) and the RRMSE convergence limit ε (the default value of ε is 0.01) in the non-resonant energy range, with the initial total number of energy segments set to $I=1$.

Step 2, calculate the reference flux and calculated flux in the current energy segment according to the Eqs. (10) and (11), then compute the RRMSE in the current energy segment using Eq. (12). If the RRMSE is within the convergence limit ε , record the current energy segment and proceed to judge the RRMSE of the next energy segment in the order of energy segments until all energy segments are calculated; if the RRMSE does not meet the convergence limit, proceed to Step 3.

Step 3, bisect the current energy segment into two energy segments according to the logarithmic energy, and return to Step 2.

2.2.2. Resonant Energy Range

In the resonant energy range, using a uniform dilation order for data processing across the full energy range leads to a dilemma, due to the large differences in resonance peak distribution. In the low-energy range (sparse resonance peaks), a low dilation order suffices to accurately capture the position and intensity of discrete peaks. However, this setting fails in the high-energy range (dense resonance peaks), causing loss of many resonance signal details and incomplete feature extraction. Conversely, increasing the dilation order to suit the high-energy range (enabling fine resolution of dense peaks) results in over-resolution in the low-energy range—greatly raising computing resource consumption and lowering analysis efficiency.

To balance calculation accuracy and efficiency, a hierarchical refinement strategy is adopted: the resonant energy range is divided into multiple refined segments based on energy characteristics, with the optimal dilation order dynamically matched to each sub-interval. This segment-adaptive method ensures resonance peaks in each segment have roughly the same scale, achieving high-precision resolution of dense peaks while avoiding redundant calculations in sparse ranges. Detailed steps follow:

Step 1, Divide the entire resonant energy range into I refined energy segments according to equal logarithmic energy (the default value of I is 256). The initial dilation order of all energy segments is set to 5, and the upper limit of the translation order of each segment is $N_{\text{max}}^{\text{Res}}$ (the default value of $N_{\text{max}}^{\text{Res}}$ is 300). Due to the large energy span of the resonant energy range, to ensure calculation accuracy, the convergence limit ε_i in each segment varies according to the reaction rate value in the segment, and the calculation formula is as follows:

$$\varepsilon_i = -\varepsilon \log \left[\frac{T_i}{\max_i(T_i)} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$T_i = \int_{u_i}^{u_{i-1}} S'(u) du \quad (14)$$

Step 2, calculate the RRMSE in the current energy segment using the Eq. (12). If the RRMSE is within the convergence limit ε_i , record the current energy segment structure and proceed to judge the error of the next energy segment in the order of energy until all energy segments are calculated;

Step 3, if the RRMSE exceeds the convergence limit ε_i , increase the dilation order of the current energy segment by 1 and return to Step 2

Step 4, after calculating all energy segments, merge adjacent energy segments with the same dilation order into a single energy segment. Meanwhile, for energy segments where the translation order exceeds the limit, split them into z energy segments according to equal logarithmic energy (using the following formula) while keeping the dilation order unchanged:

$$z = \text{int}\left[\frac{N^i}{N^{\max}}\right] + 1 \quad (15)$$

Step 5, update the current energy segment structure and the expansion order of each segment, and return to Step 2 until the energy segment structure and the expansion order of each segment remain unchanged. The adaptive parameter calculation ends, and the final adaptive scheme is output.

Using the energy segment structure and the expansion order within each segment determined by the above adaptive discretization and dynamic expansion order matching scheme for different energy ranges, the neutron transport equation is calculated, and the accurate solution of the continuous-energy deterministic neutron transport equation under real material compositions can be obtained.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The Monte Carlo software NECP-MCX[15] was used as the reference solution to calculate the infinite uniform medium problem.

3.1. Adaptive results

To verify the proposed method under representative PWR conditions, a uniform UO_2 fuel lattice was selected. The materials were homogenized via volume weighting based on the volume fractions of the fuel, cladding, and coolant. The resulting atomic densities are listed in Table I.

Table I. Compositions.

Nuclide	Atomic Density ($10^{24}\text{atom}/\text{cm}^3$)	Nuclide	Atomic Density ($10^{24}\text{atom}/\text{cm}^3$)
^1H	1.849588E-02	^{94}Zr	8.368696E-04
^{16}O	5.230841E-02	^{96}Zr	1.346694E-04
^{90}Zr	2.476936E-03	^{235}U	2.325926E-04
^{91}Zr	5.386777E-04	^{238}U	7.425734E-03
^{92}Zr	8.224431E-04		

The energy segment division structures of the resonant and non-resonant energy ranges of the UO_2 fuel material region obtained by calculation using the default program parameters are shown in Tables II and III, respectively.

Table II Non-resonance energy range energy segments division scheme

Energy/MeV	Energy /MeV	Energy /MeV	Energy /MeV	Energy /MeV
1.00000e-11	4.18139e-7	1.01492e-6	4.99160E-02	2.00000E+01
2.34035e-10	5.09215e-7	1.12001e-6	1.63650E+00	/
5.47722e-9	6.20127e-7	1.36396e-6	1.90140E+00	/
2.64972e-8	7.55198e-7	3.00000e-6	4.06570E+00	/
1.28186e-7	8.33395e-7	/	4.96590E+00	/
2.81943e-7	9.19689e-7	/	1.00000E+01	/

Table III Resonance energy range energy segments division scheme

Energy/MeV	Energy /MeV				
3.00000E-06	3.69180E-05	1.39500E-04	3.53590E-04	2.39730E-03	1.11380E-02
4.67800E-06	3.68590E-05	1.46660E-04	3.90760E-04	2.70020E-03	1.23090E-02
6.63130E-06	3.87870E-05	1.63060E-04	4.19090E-04	2.99620E-03	1.36040E-02
6.71700E-06	3.97230E-05	1.67520E-04	5.01760E-04	3.22956E-03	1.49000E-02
6.74230E-06	4.92590E-05	1.88100E-04	5.39150E-04	3.48110E-03	1.61999E-02
6.79200E-06	5.17850E-05	1.90200E-04	5.77150E-04	3.77650E-03	1.85850E-02
9.87700E-06	5.40600E-05	2.00960E-04	6.00120E-04	4.09730E-03	2.26900E-02
2.07680E-05	6.58100E-05	2.12110E-04	6.18830E-04	4.52830E-03	2.60900E-02
2.09760E-05	6.63640E-05	2.35510E-04	7.48520E-04	5.00450E-03	2.73940E-02
2.10600E-05	7.93680E-05	2.41800E-04	9.82500E-04	5.53080E-03	4.08680E-02
2.25240E-05	8.39390E-05	2.68300E-04	1.13470E-03	6.11250E-03	4.99160E-02
2.46580E-05	1.02105E-04	2.76470E-04	1.23470E-03	6.75530E-03	/
3.16930E-05	1.13470E-04	2.88370E-04	1.34360E-03	7.46590E-03	/
3.30870E-05	1.15480E-04	2.95920E-04	1.58620E-03	8.25100E-03	/
3.45390E-05	1.16520E-04	3.19930E-04	1.81180E-03	9.11880E-03	/
3.56480E-05	1.17580E-04	3.35320E-04	2.08410E-03	1.00780E-02	/

The polynomial expansion order for each energy segment in the non-resonant range is 2, while the dilation order of the wavelet scaling function for each segment in the resonant range is shown in Figure 1. Unlike the fixed energy segment structure (WIMS-69 group structure), which needs repeated trial calculations to determine the dilation order of each segment, the adaptive method can accurately lock the optimal dilation order of each segment via a dynamic matching mechanism. As shown in the Figure 1, the order selected by the adaptive method offers significant advantages over manually selected results in most energy segments of the resonant range.

Figure 1 Dilation Order of Each Energy Segment

Figure 2 Translation Order of Each Energy Segment

Figure 2 intuitively compares the number of translation order for each energy segment under fixed versus adaptive energy segment structures: the maximum number per segment is only 295 for the adaptive structure, significantly lower than the 1042 for the fixed one. This shows that the adaptive energy segment structure can notably reduce the neutron transport calculation load per segment, effectively shortening calculation time and greatly improving efficiency.

3.2. Neutron transport calculation results

Verification results in Figure 3 and Figure 4 present a comparative analysis between the adaptive technique, the WIMS-69 non-adaptive benchmark, and the reference values. Notably, the WIMS-69

structure is used only as a fixed energy mesh, with the same continuous-energy function expansion applied within each segment. Calculated values agree well with reference values, with most relative deviations within 1% (maximum 2.7%), while eigenvalue results in Table IV have a maximum deviation within 50 pcm. Unlike the fixed energy mesh structure, which requires repetitive trial-and-error to determine the optimal expansion orders, the proposed adaptive technique requires only 5.1 seconds to generate the adaptive parameters for this test case.

Figure 3 Flux of adaptive Energy Segment

Figure 4 Flux of non-adaptive Energy Segment

 Table IV Comparison of k_{eff}

Reference k_{eff}	Adaptive k_{eff}	Δk_{eff} /pcm	Non-adaptive k_{eff}	Δk_{eff} /pcm
1.17031 ± 0.00003	1.16989	-42	1.16985	-46

Table V shows the comparison of the calculation time of full-energy-domain neutron transport under the fixed energy segment structure and the adaptive energy segment structure. The data results clearly indicate that compared with the traditional fixed energy segment structure, the use of the adaptive energy segment structure for neutron transport calculation significantly reduces the time consumption by approximately two-thirds, greatly improving the calculation efficiency and highlighting the efficiency and superiority of the adaptive method in practical applications.

Table V Comparison results of calculation time

	Fixed energy segment structure	Adaptive energy segment structure
Computation time/s	3.4	0.9

4. CONCLUSIONS

To solve issues of traditional multi-group approximation-based deterministic neutron transport calculations (e.g., multi-group database creation and complex resonance calculations), this study proposes an all-energy-domain coupled continuous-energy deterministic method via function expansion: polynomial basis functions expand neutron energy spectra in non-resonant ranges and wavelet basis functions in resonant ranges, with an adaptive energy segment discretization and expansion order dynamic matching mechanism (judging segment rationality by relative root-mean-square error to adjust structure/order for efficiency). A developed program tested on UOX fuel shows good agreement with Monte Carlo software NECP-MCX—most relative deviations <1% (max $\leq 2.7\%$), eigenvalue deviation <50pcm—verifying feasibility and eliminating multi-group approximation-induced resonance effects; currently limited to single-region adaptive analysis, future work will include multi-region scenarios to build a unified scheme for complex multi-material reactor core conditions.

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